

Senior IRB and Regulatory Manager Adele Ndiaye (she/her)

"I value being a regulatory resource for PIs and my colleagues while also actively supporting innovative and impactful research."

Bio

After completing a Bachelor's degree in psychology, Adele accepted a position in the compliance department of a large healthcare organization. She found the work appealing to her analytical inclination, and she began to acquire all the regulatory knowledge she could, to become an invaluable resource to her colleagues. When she transitioned to an IRB associate role at an academic medical center, she found that she was able to further apply her skills by streamlining protocol reviews, analyzing patterns in the study activation process, and implementing process improvements at all stages. Within two years she was promoted to Senior IRB and Regulatory Associate, and within five years to IRB and Regulatory Manager. Daily, Adele employs her constantly updated regulatory knowledge; communication, people, and teambuilding skills; data and information management expertise for streamlining workflows, file naming, and information documentation; and strategic planning skills as she forms and leads committees to improve protocol review and IRB panel procedures. Adele assists and supports her colleagues in achieving their professional development goals, through active mentoring and by advocating for professional development support from the university.

Education: BS: Psychology, CIP certification

Years of experience: 8

Work location: Hybrid between office and remote work on her laptop

Goals

- Ensure protection of human subjects while supporting cutting-edge research
- Be a trustworthy source of regulatory knowledge for her institution and team
- Ensure consistent application of regulations in the review process

Software attitude & use

- Solid user of software interfaces; needs consistent remote access to reporting and database tools, which is sometimes a challenge
- General: Microsoft Office Suite and Google Workspace
- Collaboration: Zoom, Teams, Box
- Specialized resources include websites (e.g., FDA, OHRP, HHS, Office of Civil Rights, FDA and NIH listservs), and research administration and IRB database systems

Outputs

- Presentations and posters at conferences
- Occasional guest speaker at department meetings, classes
- White papers and internal compliance memos

Pain Points

- High workloads; tight review timelines
- More funding needed to hire, train team
- Cross-institution IRBs are meant to streamline but often do the opposite
- Insufficient training, especially for early career researchers, in research ethics and study design
- Researchers requesting above-and-beyond help with writing protocols

Motivators

- Help PIs understand what their protocols should include; to help IRB panelists understand regulatory requirements
- Be fully up-to-date with HHS, FDA, HIPAA regulations; local mandates, requirements for forms and templates
- Be fully conversant about regulations to be able to solve problems through discussions
- Lead her team in a collaborative and supportive way

Wants/Needs

- More trust, less resistance from PIs
- Time to adequately train her team and to provide constructive feedback
- Assurance that PIs are fully trained in Responsible Conduct of Research and research ethics and that they grasp the ethics behind regulations
- Effective technology, electronic tracking systems
- Time to review issues with PI before the board is convened to avoid resubmission

Professional Development

Adele's institution provides support for her to take the Certified IRB Professional (CIP exam); supporting 30 hours of study per year to maintain this certification

Adele constantly updates her skills through literature and training sessions on new scientific, regulatory, and technical info affecting human subjects research

Adele is a member of Public Responsibility in Medicine and Research (PRIM&R), local IRB consortia, and attends conferences such as AAHRPP (Association for the Accreditation of Human Research Protection Programs)